

FUZZY LOGIC BASED ENERGY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR OFF-GRID CONNECTED PV PUMPED HYDRO ELECTRICITY SYSTEM

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878284>

Abstract: The study is aimed at optimizing the performance of solar pumped hydro storage system for power system resiliency. Renewable energy sources, despite being environmentally friendly, often exhibit varying degrees of intermittency that poses a challenge in the provision of uninterrupted power supply to end users. Since the energy produced by the primary PV source is not constant especially at night and during unfavorable weather conditions, an energy storage system in the form of pumped hydroelectricity was introduced. The seamless integration of pumped hydro storage systems with renewable energy sources makes it an essential component for future energy systems as they offer a range of unique advantages such as voltage support, load shifting, grid stability and system resilience. However, management of power remains a challenging issue faced by renewable power generation. To mitigate this challenge, advanced control and optimization techniques, along with energy management systems, are employed to ensure efficient operation. This study proposes an intelligent valve system that monitors varying solar irradiance and reservoir water level based on a fuzzy logic algorithm for effective control of a centrifugal pump to ensure continuous supply and load demand consistency. The hybrid system was designed in the MATLAB/Simulink environment using several models of subsystems such as a solar array DC-DC boost converter, induction motor, and centrifugal pump. The system dynamic model was developed based on the sizing of the system. The results obtained show that the fuzzy logic controller was able to monitor the variation in irradiance and water level and actuate the control valve to change the direction of flow and the local controller was capable of extracting maximum power from the PV panels with tracking efficiency exceeding 99.5%. This shows that the proposed fuzzy logic controller effectively managed the operation of the pumped hydroelectricity for appropriate energy supply according to fuzzy rules to ensure continuous supply and load demand consistency.

Keywords: Centrifugal Pump, Hydro Turbine, Fuzzy Logic Controller, Boost Converter, PV Array

1.0 Introduction

A great way to mitigate intermittency that arises with renewable energy is through the use of a hybrid system where different renewable energy sources are combined with an energy storage system. Energy storage systems are key components of a HRES to maintain the power quality and reliability. It helps to provide a buffer for periods of imbalance with power demanded and supplied. There are various energy storage technologies in use such as fuel cell, battery, flywheel, super capacitor, hydro pump etc, (Adewumi & Adelekan, 2015).

Renewable energy sources, despite being environmentally friendly, often exhibit varying degrees of intermittency that poses challenges for consistent power production which are crucial for providing uninterrupted power supply to end users. The seamless integration of pumped hydro storage systems with renewable energy sources make it an essential component for future energy systems as they offer a range of unique advantages such as voltage support, load shifting, grid stability and system resilience. However, a key challenge faced in integrating renewable energy sources with pumped hydro storage system is in management of the intermittent and variable nature of renewable power generation. To mitigate this challenge, an advanced control and optimization techniques, along with energy management systems, is employed to ensure efficient operation. This study proposes an intelligent valve system that monitors varying solar irradiance and reservoir water level based on fuzzy logic algorithm for effective control of centrifugal pump to ensure continuous supply and load demand consistency.

For this study, Solar PV with pumped hydro storage system was used to provide efficient and reliable power supply. While the solar PV system was used to pump water from a lower reservoir, the hydro pump storage was used to provide a buffer during period of low irradiance. The hydro storage system was used because hydro generation is the most sustainable of all the renewable energy sources.

2.0 Literature Review

Pumped hydro-electric storage is a technology which is based mainly on two reservoirs placed at two different locations and two different heights, one at a higher location, the other at a lower location, and water is pumped into the upper reservoir when electric power is not very much in use (off-peak). Then when electricity becomes highly needed, the stored water in the upper reservoir is released and passes through the hydro turbines to produce electricity (Vahid and Mahdi, 2021)

Blakers *et al.* (2021) presented a review of storage systems based on pumped hydro energy (PHE). When describing hydroelectricity production, it was mentioned that in the powerhouse, both the generator and the turbine are kept or housed and for majority of cases pumped hydro storage is river based and always in conjunction with generation of hydroelectric. It should be noted however, that though the authors mentioned that the pump and the turbine are kept in the powerhouse, both the pump and the turbine can be separated, kept at different locations reasonably far away from each other. The turbine can act as a turbine and as a pump. To act as a pump, power is supplied to the generator which then causes the turbine and the generator to spin in directions opposite to each other and then pump water to a higher reservoir from a lower one. A situation where the pump and the turbine are located a long distance apart was not considered.

Hoffstaedt *et al.* (2022) considered a low-head pumped hydro storage, with special attention given to challenges and applicable technologies in connection with low head pumped storage system. The authors stated that there is usually a reduction in the stability of the grid which is due to a fast-growing share of intermittent renewable sources of energy in any electrical grids. As mentioned, the application of pumped hydro is limited traditionally to some topographic features. Therefore, expanding the range of operation to low-head situations was considered by the authors as vital in unlocking the general potential of great deployment to key areas that have been covered. The low-head pumped hydro storage is considered to have a range of 2m to 30m. It was found that for low-head high-flow application, pumped turbines of axial flow, having variable speed drivers are more suitable.

Majidniya *et al.* (2017) made a comparison of grid-tied options and off-grid-pumped hydro system for power generation using internal reforming solid oxide fuel cell (IRSOFC) and a horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT).

As the implies, the wind turbine used was placed along the horizontal axis. It was noted that the output of the horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) was not stable at all. However, the authors argued that combing the two techniques, the HAWT and IRSOFC, and keeping the IRSOFC's fuel rate under control, the combined system gave a stable power.

Hamdy *et al.* (2018) proposed a hybrid system that comprises a pumped storage hydro-electric power, wind energy and a solar PV and developed a mathematical model to describe the operation of the model proposed. The hydropower plant makes use of water from the sea as its lower reservoir while a tank is built and installed high up to serve as the upper reservoir. An investigation of the impact of the proposed hybrid system on the grid utility was carried out under different scenarios. The obtained results after the investigations revealed the ability of the proposed hybrid system to minimize the energy exchange with the grid.

Mariana and Helena (2020) also conducted research on hybrid pumped hydro storage and presented a method that is based on multi criteria evaluation. There was a combination of three sources such as pump and turbine with three different capacities, 2, 4, and 6MW; different volume capacities of reservoir; and PV solar and wind powers of 0.54-1.6 and 4-5MW respectively. It was found that a combination of the hydro, wind and PV solar panel having capacities 4, 5, and 0.54MW with the volume of reservoir at 378000 cubic meters was the best alternative, having less return on investments and provided about 72% yearly consumption satisfaction. The authors argued that the use of pumped hydro storage with PV and wind provides the real solution that increases reliability and flexibility and to realize energy autonomy.

An investigation of wind power integration with small hydroelectric power plants was carried out by Singh *et al.* (2018). The idea behind the work was that an integration of renewable energy source into any part of the grid that is weak will enhance the stability of the system. Hydropower reservoirs, whether they are pumped storage plants or conventional plants, provide large scale energy storage system.

In the work done by Kun *et al.* (2011) a presentation of maximized-wind-penetration in wind hydro pumped storage was made. The objective was to find an alternative solution to develop power as conventional generation point. The authors recommended an investigation of operational efficiency, system performance, and optimal design.

3.0 Materials and Method

3.1 Materials

The materials used includes;

- ❖ PV Array
- ❖ Boost Converter
- ❖ Inverter
- ❖ Induction Motor
- ❖ Centrifugal Pump
- ❖ Water Reservoir

3.2 Method

A fuzzy logic controller was used to predict fluctuations in solar insolation and reservoir water level to control the operation of a centrifugal pump used in hydro pump storage system as shown in figure1.

Figure1: Takagi–Sugeno Fuzzy Logic Designer for Intelligent Valve Control.

3.3 Designed Procedure

3.3.1 Load Estimation

Table1 shows the list of electrical appliances and their wattages considered for this study for an estimated daily average load consumption of 430.4kWh for 100 households.

Table1: Load Specification

Load	Watt	Qty	Total Watt	hr	Watt-hr
TV	60	1	60	8	480
Radio	20	1	20	8	160
Fan	80	2	160	8	1280
Charger	5	3	15	8	120
Bulbs	20	4	80	8	640
Fridge	100	1	100	8	800
Total kWhr					4.304
For 100 household daily kWhr					430.4

3.3.2 Formation of Membership Function

Figure 2 Membership Function for Solar Irradiance

Figure 2 shows the membership function for solar irradiance respectively. The value ranges from 0 to 1000 with three (3) linguistic variable namely; L for low irradiance, M for moderate irradiance, and H for high irradiance respectively.

Figure 3 Membership Function for Water Level

Figure 3 shows the membership function for water level. The value ranges from 0 to 3 with three (3) linguistic variable namely; L for low irradiance, M for moderate irradiance, and H for high irradiance respectively.

3.3.4 Formation of Fuzzy Logic Rule for Intelligent Valve Control

Table 2: FLC Decision Matrix

Intelligent Control	Valve	Water Level		
		L	M	H
Irradiance	L	P ₀ ,T ₀	P ₀ ,T ₁	P ₀ ,T ₁
	M	P ₁ ,T ₀	P ₁ ,T ₀	P ₀ ,T ₁
	H	P ₁ ,T ₀	P ₁ ,T ₀	P ₀ ,T ₀

Table 2 shows the the fuzzy logic decision matrix rule constructed for implementation of intelligent valve control. The fuzzy Rule is summarized as follows;

1. If irradiance is Low and water level is Low then Pump is Close and Turbine is Close
2. If irradiance is Low and water level is Moderate then Pump is Close and Turbine is Open
3. If irradiance is Low and water level is High then Pump is Close and Turbine is Open
4. If irradiance is Moderate and water level is Low then Pump is Open and Turbine is Close
5. If irradiance is Moderate and water level is Moderate then Pump is Open and Turbine is Close
6. If irradiance is Moderate and water level is High then Pump is Close and Turbine is Open
7. If irradiance is High and water level is Low then Pump is Open and Turbine is Close
8. If irradiance is High and water level is Moderate then Pump is Open and Turbine is Close
9. If irradiance is High and water level is High then Pump is Close and Turbine is Close

3.3.5 Determination of Total Dynamic Head (TDH)

$$THD = h_p + h_s + [L_t + \sum(n_f * f_e)] * \frac{f_h}{100} \quad (1)$$

where

h_p : pumping level

h_s : vertical rise

L_t : Total length of pipe

f_e : Fittings of the pipe, in feet, which has a standard value in feet, depending on the pipe's diameter

n_f : Number of same fittings in the system

f_h : Friction loss of head per 100 feet of pipe, depending on the pipe's diameter and flow rate.

3.3.6 Determination of Pump Power

$$\text{Pump power } (P_h) = \frac{Q * \rho g * THD}{1000} \quad (2)$$

where

Q : flow rate m^3/s

ρ : density of water kg/m^3

g : acceleration due to gravity in m/s

THD : total dynamic head in m

3.3.7 Determination of Motor Capacity

$$\text{Motor Power } (P_m) = \frac{\text{Pump Power}}{\text{efficiency}} \quad (3)$$

where

P_h : hydraulic power

η : pump efficiency 80%

3.3.8 Photovoltaic System Sizing

$$\text{Pump use} = P_m * T_{op} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{PV Energy} = \text{Pump use} * S_L \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Array Power} = \frac{\text{PV Energy}}{S_H} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Number of Panel} = \frac{\text{Array Power}}{\text{Panel Rating}} \quad (7)$$

Where

P_m : pump power

T_{op} : operating time

S_L : system loss

S_H : average sun hour per day

3.3.9 Boost Converter System

Directly supplying the DC photovoltaic power to the electric load may be inappropriate because the voltage gradient of PV cells is adjustable due to the position of the operating point. The solution is to use DC- DC converters to step up or step down the available voltages to the required value so as to maintain a constant supply to the system

Figure 4 DC- DC Boost Converter

Figure6 Solar Irradiance

Figure7 Reservoir Water Level

Table3: Parameters for computing THD

h_p	59.06ft
h_s	39.4ft
L_t	105ft
n_f	1elbow
f_e	8 for $2\frac{1}{2}$ " diameter pipe
f_h	9.58ft

Table4: Parameters for computing Pump Size

THD	109.23ft
Q	0.0327m ³ /s
ρg	1000kg/m ³
η	80%

Table:5 Specification for PV Array

Parameters	Symbol	Values
Parallel String	Np	14
Series connected module per string	Ns	14
Maximum Power	Pmax (W)	305.226
Voltage @ MP	Vmp (V)	54.7
Current @ MP	Imp (A)	5.58
Open Circuit Voltage	Voc (V)	64.2
Short Circuit Current	Isc (A)	5.96
Cell per Module		96
Irradiance		1000w/m ²

Table:6 Specification for Boost Converter

Paramters	Values
Vinput	536.9V
Voutput	633.5V
Rated Power	49.82kW
Switching Frequency (fsw)	5kHz
Current Ripple (ΔI)	5%
Voltage Ripple (ΔV)	1%
Inductance L	3.539 mH
Capacitance C	378.58 μF
Load Resistor R	8.06 Ω
Duty Cycle D	0.233

Figure8 Flow Chart of the Energy Management Strategy

4.0 Result and Discussion

Figure 9: Maximum Power Extracted from PV Array

Figure 9 shows the plot of maximum power extracted from the PV array under varying irradiance as shown in figure 6 above. The performance of a PV array strongly depends on operating environmental conditions such as operating temperature, solar insolation, and array configuration. A quick look at Figure 9 shows that a maximum power of 60kW was extracted from the array at a very fast rise time and stabilizes at the maximum power point with no oscillations which are some of the advantages of the fuzzy logic controllers. For 8hrs, a total of 480kWh energy will be supplied by the PV array at standard irradiance of 1000w/m^2 and a constant temperature of 25°C .

Figure 10: FLC Rule Viewer for Pump Mode

Figure 10 shows the rule viewer display for intelligent control of hydro pump storage system. The rule viewer allows for the interpretation of the entire fuzzy inference process at once and indicates the shape of certain membership functions that influences the overall result. For this study, nine (9) rules were considered but for actuating the pump mode of the hydro pump storage system rule 7 and 8 are used to roadmap the process.

Figure 11: Surface View for Pump Mode

Figure 11 shows the surface view of the pump mode according to the developed fuzzy rule and inference engine. The fuzzy logic controller monitors variation in irradiance and water level and if irradiance is high say from 600w/m^2 and above, and the water level is low or moderate, say less than 1.5m. The FLC output 1 showing valve opening for pump mode and 0 valve closing for turbine mode.

Figure 12: FLC Rule Viewer for Turbine Mode

Similarly, the rule viewer for actuating the turbine mode of the hydro pump storage system is shown in Figure 12. The rule viewer displays nine (9) rules. However, rule 2 and 3 were used to roadmap the process for actuating the turbine mode and shows how the shape of certain membership functions influences the overall result.

Figure 12 shows the surface view of the turbine mode according to the developed fuzzy rule and inference engine. The fuzzy logic controller monitors variation in irradiance and water level and if irradiance is low, say less than 400 w/m^2 and water level is moderate or high, say from 1.5m and above, the controller will actuate the control valve to change the direction of rotation to turbine mode.

Figure 13: Surface View for Turbine Mode

Figure14 FLC intelligent Valve Opening

Figure 14 shows the intelligent valve opening and closing scenario for fuzzy logic controlled hybrid power system. From 0.00-0.8:45am the irradiance is low and water level high See figure 6 and 7 for variation in irradiance and water level. The fuzzy logic controller monitors variation in irradiance and water level and if irradiance is low and water level is moderate or high, the controller output 1 for turbine mode and 0 for pump mode indicating the control valve to change direction to turbine mode. Similarly, from 0.8:45am-3:00pm when the irradiance is high and water level either low or moderate, the controller output 0 for turbine mode and 1 for pump mode indicating the control valve to change direction of rotation to pump mode. From 4:00pm as the irradiance gradually drop to zero, the controller output 1 for turbine mode and 0 for pump mode indicating change of direction to turbine mode.

5.0 Conclusion

This study examined the model and operation characteristics of hybrid photovoltaic system and Pumped Hydro System. As the energy demands and the environmental issues like global warming skyrocket on daily basis. The awareness in adopting clean energy sources as one solution that can address the ever increasing energy and global warming crisis of is growing at a remarkable rate. The study gives a technical and economic insight on the viability of the water re-using techniques of hydro pumped storage system. The techniques permit storage of excess energy for later use which will decrease fuel and emission cost and helps to the integration of renewable energy in to the power grid.

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